
An Empirical Assessment of Tourist Preferences and Sustainable Tourism Practices in Valparai, Western Ghats

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ABSTRACT

Valparai is one of the important places that make Coimbatore district proud. Valparai is part of western ghats which is recognized by UNESCO world heritage site. This study aims to explore the reason behind tourist visits Valparai and their preference towards eco-tourism. The data is collected from 200 respondent through purposive sampling method. The collected data were analyzed through simple percentage, Garret ranking analysis and One-way Anova. The finding of the study holds significant value to the development towards sustainable tourism in Valparai and also helps to policymakers to align the strategies towards ecological protection.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Valparai is one of the important places that make Coimbatore district proud. Valparai is part of western ghats which is recognized by UNESCO world heritage site. Valparai is also known as 7th heaven. It is city as tourist destination with tea and coffee plantations, waterfalls cascading from the mountains like silver wires, and huge dams that store and hold back river water. Main pillar of this region to maintain an eco-tourism is local communities, NGO's and forest department. NGO's and forest department collaborate with local communities educate them to wild life monitoring and guide to tourists. Eco-tourist

plays a vital role in shaping a sustainable tourism practice, it is essential to know their understanding and preference towards environmental and cultural significance about Valparai. This study aims to explore the reason behind tourist visits Valparai and their preference towards eco-tourism. The finding of the study will use to develop the sustainable tourism that meet visitors' expectation and also protect the environmental goals.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mohd Rusli Yacob et al, (2011) conducted study with the objective of to investigate the tourist perception on ecotourism management and development. The results found that tourists have different preferences against their profiles in term of ecotourism resource management and maintenance as well as on revenue implementation. The results provide useful implications on ecotourism resources management in marine park. **Nguyen Nguyen Dang and Ali Abdulbaqi Ameen Ali (2018)** made a study to Analyze the Tourist satisfaction towards service quality of traveling companies. The result of the study indicating that the visitors' satisfaction had the most positive effect to the sustainable tourism development. **Rani . S (2020)** did a study to find out how Level of satisfaction tourist attained from ecotourism in India. Concluded her study as, the visitors from various places of home and host country perceived that there is an improvement in the accessibility of the tourist places. **Shreyashi Kundu et al., (2022)** made a study to Find out how Level of Satisfaction Tourist Attained from Ecotourism in India. The conclusions of the study show that the great majority of respondents were local tourists and they have positive relationships between an experience with ecotourism in India. **Sihem DEKHILI and Mohamed Akli ACHABOU (2015)** to examine the study to define the contents of the concept of "ecotourism" from the tourists' point of view and to determine the various expectations. The results show that the concept of ecotourism evokes for the tourists essentially an environmental dimension related to the planet preservation, the visited sites' protection, the natural and sustainable character of the travel.

3. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Tourism in Valparai had both opportunities and challenger for the region's environment and local communities. Tourism can generate income as well as promote economic development, it is also damaging ecosystem and disrupting traditional way of life. To ensure the sustainable tourism, it is essential to understand tourists understanding and preference for eco-tourism practices in Valparai. In this study aim to find the reason for visiting Valparai among tourist and their understanding and preferences towards

eco-tourism practice. This study aims to provide understanding that can inform sustainable tourism in Valparai.

4. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- ✚ To find the reason for visiting Valparai among the tourists.
- ✚ To discover the tourist preferences towards eco-friendly tourism practices in Valparai

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is mainly based on primary data. The data is collected from 200 respondent through purposive sampling method. The collected data were analyzed through simple percentage, Garret ranking analysis and One-way Anova.

6. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

6.1. Simple Percentage

TABLE 1. SOCIO- ECONOMIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Socio-Economic Profile	Sub Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Age	Below 19	22	11
	20 to 41	132	66
	Above 42	46	23
Gender	Male	98	49
	Female	102	51
Area of Residence	Rural	99	49
	Urban	101	51
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	13	6
	Up to HSC	54	27
	Under Graduate	80	40
	Post Graduate	37	19
	Professional	4	2
Marital Status	Others	12	6
	Married	96	48
Family Type	Unmarried	104	52
	Joint Family	66	33
Occupation	Nuclear Family	134	67
	Student	75	38
	Daily wage earners	19	9
	Govt Employee	6	3

	Private Employee	46	23
	Business	19	9
	Agriculturist	22	11
	Homemaker	13	7
No of members in family	Up to 2	167	83
	3 -4 Members	30	15
	Above 4 Members	3	2
Earning members in family	One	62	31
	Two	106	53
	Three	27	13
	Above 3	5	3
Respondent Monthly Income	Up to Rs. 30,000	140	70
	Rs. 30,001-Rs. 50,000	33	17
	Rs. 50,001- Rs. 1,00,000	16	8
	Above Rs. 1,00,000	11	5
Family Monthly Income	Up to Rs. 50,000	106	53
	Rs. 50,001- Rs. 1,00,000	50	25
	Above Rs. 1,00,000	44	22

It is observed that 49% (98 tourists) were male, while 51% (102 tourists) were female. The majority of the tourists, 52% (104 tourists), were unmarried individuals, while 48% (96 tourists) were married. In terms of age, 11% (22 tourists) were below 19 years old, the vast majority, 66% (132 tourists), were between 20 and 41 years old, and 23% (46 tourists) were 42 years old or above. The majority of the tourists, 51% (101 tourists), resided in urban areas, while 49% (99 tourists) resided in rural areas.

When the education levels of the individuals included in the sample are examined, it is observed that the largest group, 40% (80 tourists), were undergraduates, followed by 27% (54 tourists) who had education up to HSC, and 19% (37 tourists) who were post-graduates. Additionally, 6% (13 tourists) were illiterate, 2% (4 tourists) had professional qualifications, and another 6% (12 tourists) had other qualifications. In terms of family type, the majority, 67% (134 tourists), had nuclear families, while 33% (66 tourists) had joint families. The most common occupation among the tourists was student, accounting for 38% (75 tourists), followed by private employees at 23% (46 tourists) and agriculturists at 11% (22 tourists). Daily wage earners and business owners each constituted 9% (19 tourists). Government employees made up 3% (6 tourists), and homemakers represented 7% (13 tourists).

Regarding the number of family members, a significant majority, 83% (167 tourists), belonged to families with up to 2 members, followed by 15% (30 tourists) in families with 3-4 members, and only 2% (3 tourists) in families with more than 4 members. In terms of earning members in the family, 53% (106 tourists) reported having two earning members, 31% (62 tourists) had one earning member, 13% (27 tourists) had three earning members, and 3% (5 tourists) had more than three earning members.

Concerning the tourists' monthly income, 70% (140 tourists) earned up to Rs. 30,000, 17% (33 tourists) earned between Rs. 30,001 and Rs. 50,000, 8% (16 tourists) earned between Rs. 50,001 and Rs. 1,00,000, and 5% (11 tourists) earned above Rs. 1,00,000. Looking at the family monthly income, 53% (106 tourists) belonged to families with an income up to Rs. 50,000, 25% (50 tourists) had a family income between Rs. 50,001 and Rs. 1,00,000, and 22% (44 tourists) had a family income above Rs. 1,00,000. It concluded that the tourists were predominantly female, unmarried, and residing in urban areas. The largest group had an undergraduate degree, came from nuclear families, and were students. A significant majority belonged to smaller families with up to two members and reported having two earning members. The majority of the tourists had a personal monthly income of up to Rs. 30,000, and over half belonged to families with a monthly income of up to Rs. 50,000.

6.2. GARRET RANKING

In order to find the most preferred reasons for visiting Valparai, the tourist was asked to rank all the factors in order of preference. Then, the Garret Ranking tool has been used to find the most preferred reason for visiting Valparai among the tourist.

TABLE 2. REASON FOR VISITING VALPARAI

Factor/Rank	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Rank 4	Rank 5	Rank 6	Rank 7	Rank 8	AVG.	Rank
Scenic Beauty	1840	1608	2340	1749	611	920	544	560	50.86	5
Attractive Climate	1600	3216	1680	1696	658	320	960	400	52.65	3
Pollution Free Environment	2480	2613	1500	1749	705	840	416	460	53.82	1
Wild Life	3200	335	600	2862	2115	1000	384	180	53.38	2
Viewing and Accessibility	1200	603	1920	1484	1739	720	1184	480	46.65	7
Nearness	2240	1005	1980	371	2538	920	992	180	51.13	4
Cost Effectiveness	400	2077	1860	689	423	480	1440	1080	42.25	8
Relaxation and Wellness	3120	1675	120	106	611	2760	608	620	48.10	6

Based on above table the first Rank, is Pollution Free Environment. This suggests that tourists highly value the unspoiled and fresh nature of Valparai. the factor Wild Life Viewing and Safari

Experiences is Ranked second, signifying a strong attraction towards the opportunities for wildlife encounters in the area. Attractive Climate is measured the third most significant factor, highlighting the significance of enjoyable weather in portrayal visitors.

Nearness to the destination got fourth Rank, significant that proximity plays a notable role in tourists' choices. Scenic Beauty is Ranked fifth, showing that while valued. Relaxation and Wellness opportunities are Ranked sixth, indicating that these aspects contribute to the destination's appeal but are not main drivers for most visitors. Accessibility to Valparai is Ranked seventh, implying that it is a consideration but not a major deciding factor. Finally, Cost Effectiveness is perceived as Ranking eighth, indicating that the expense of visiting is not a main concern for the majority of tourists to Valparai.

The Garrett ranking method has been used to determine the activities that tourist prioritize during their visit of Valparai. This methodology helps to identify the most common preferred activities, based on preference of tourism in Valparai.

TABLE 3. ACTIVITIES PRIORITIZE DURING THE VISIT OF VALPARAI

Factor/Rank	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Rank 4	Rank 5	Rank 6	Rank 7	Rank 8	AVG.	Rank
Visiting Wildlife Sanctuaries	6960	1943	660	1802	141	480	352	260	62.99	1
Adventure Activities (Trekking and Hiking, Bike Riding)	3040	4154	1380	530	987	920	480	160	58.26	2
Tea Garden Visit	1840	1273	5160	1113	705	560	160	340	55.76	3
Waterfalls Exploration	1520	2144	720	4240	611	360	928	120	53.22	4
Attending Fairs and Festivals	400	1005	1620	742	3008	1280	832	340	46.14	6
Historical Site Exploration (Temple, Water Dam)	1360	536	600	1007	2256	2920	512	180	46.86	5

Photography	800	1742	1260	848	987	600	2240	420	44.49	7
Tent Camps & Campfire and music	80	603	660	318	705	880	864	2180	31.45	8

The above Garrett Ranking table reveals the preferred tourist activities in the area. Visiting Wildlife Sanctuaries emerges as the most favored activity, securing the first rank (62.99), it indicates a strong interest among tourists in experiencing the local wildlife. Adventure Activities (Trekking and Hiking, Bike Riding) is the second most preferred activity (58.26), highlighting the appeal of outdoor and adventurous pursuits. Tea Garden Visit ranks third (55.76), suggesting that exploring the tea estates is a significant draw for visitors. Waterfalls Exploration holds the fourth rank (53.22), indicating a considerable interest in natural water features. Historical Site Exploration (Temple, Water Dam) is ranked fifth (46.86), showing a moderate level of interest in cultural and historical attractions. Attending Fairs and Festivals comes in at the sixth rank with (46.14), suggesting a mild interest in local cultural events. Photography is ranked seventh (44.49), indicating a lower priority for this activity among tourists. Finally, Tent Camps & Campfire and music is the least preferred activity, ranking eighth (31.45).

It concluded that the most popular tourist activities are centered around wildlife and adventure, followed by exploring tea gardens and waterfalls. This suggests that the primary attractions of this destination lie in its natural and adventurous offerings.

6.3. ONE WAY ANOVA

To find whether any different socio-economic groups exhibit varying preferences, a one-way ANOVA was conducted. This methodology employed to find if there are any statistically significant differences in the Preference Index across within socio-economic variables.

TABLE 4. PREFERENCES TOWARDS ECO-FRIENDLY TOURISM PRACTICES- ONE WAY ANOVA

INDEPENDENT VARIABLE	DEPENDENT VARIABLE	P VALUE	DECISION
Age	Preference Index	.269	Not Significant
Gender	Preference Index	.631	Not Significant

Area of Residence	Preference Index	.04	Significant
Education Qualification	Preference Index	.01	Significant
Marital Status	Preference Index	.842	Not Significant
Family Type	Preference Index	.229	Not Significant
Occupation	Preference Index	.342	Not Significant
No of members in family	Preference Index	.564	Not Significant
Earning members in family	Preference Index	.525	Not Significant
Respondent Monthly Income	Preference Index	.137	Not Significant
Family Monthly Income	Preference Index	.00	Significant

The finding shows that there are significant differences in the Preference Index across the three categories within socio-economic variables. The preference levels of respondents from rural areas are significantly different from those in urban areas. Similarly, individuals with different educational qualifications and monthly income of the family exhibit significantly determining the preference levels.

6. CONCLUSION

The finding of the study reveals that tourists place highest value on pollution-free environment. It is clearly shows that tourists are drawn mostly to the destination's unspoiled natural beauty, pleasant weather, biodiversity. The Valparai identified as destination rooted in eco-tourism practice. Furthermore, the study highlights the most preferred activity is wildlife and adventure activities followed by visiting tea plantation and waterfalls. Importantly, the study finds significant variation in preference across socio-economic groups such as education, income and residence of the respondent. The study suggests education, income and residence plays a vital role in shaping an eco-tourism behavior. These finding hold significant value to the development towards sustainable tourism in Valparai and also helps to policymakers to align the strategies towards ecological protection.

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